
58. Einstein crosses

QUASARS ALLOW the successive Gaia catalogues, and in particular their parallaxes and proper motions, to be referenced directly to an extragalactic, or ‘inertial’, reference system. Some half a million distant quasars are observed as part of the Gaia survey, and I have outlined how they are being used to define this inertial reference system in essay #12.

Many quasars show extended structures, and time variability, which complicate the construction and definition of such a reference system. But, at the same time, these structures convey important physical information about the quasars themselves. Their intrinsic variability, for example, can be used to infer properties of the black hole accretion disks which power the intense electromagnetic radiation emanating from them.

GRAVITATIONAL LENSES, due to intervening massive galaxies and clusters along the line of sight, which result (in highly aligned cases) in multiple images of the quasar itself, are particularly rich in physical insights.

Strongly lensed quasars (i.e. those which result in multiple discrete images) provide a remarkable diagnostic for a whole range of important studies, including measuring the Hubble constant at intermediate cosmic distances; constraining the properties of dark matter; inferring the structure near the event horizon of super-

massive black holes; measuring the accretion disk size; constraining the quasar broad emission line region geometry; measuring black hole spins; and testing general relativity in the strong-gravity regime.

Fortunately for the task of defining the reference system, such strongly lensed quasars are rare. But their rarity and compactness makes them difficult to find. Amongst the most keenly hunted are the quadruply-imaged ‘Einstein crosses’, which are some of the most constraining for detailed physical modelling, and where the time delays between the images brightness variations can provide constraints on the Hubble constant.

THE FIRST EINSTEIN CROSS to be discovered was QSO 2237+0305, a quasar at $z = 1.695$ nearly centred on a relatively nearby 15 mag spiral galaxy at $z = 0.0394$ (Huchra et al., 1985).

While crescents and rings resulting from gravitational lensing can be understood somewhat intuitively, it is not so obvious how such remarkable 4-image systems arise. Here, I would say, intuition is not such a helpful guide. Instead, we have to work through the mathematics, first noting that the details of the lensed images is governed by the *projected* surface mass density on the sky (i.e., in the lens plane). The four images cannot be due to a spherically symmetric lensing galaxy, but instead can arise when the lens is a triaxial ellipsoid.

Detailed lensing models with such a ‘quadrupole moment mass asymmetry’ (e.g. Chae et al., 1998) can also explain why the four images are almost circular, rather than arc-like. And they explain why the results do not contradict the ‘odd number theorem’ in gravitational lensing (viz. that there are always an *odd* number of lensed images): this is because one image (the fifth) lies right behind the foreground galaxy, and it is invisible because its magnification is always very small.

THE FIRST GRAVITATIONALLY lensed quasar, the ‘twin quasar’ QSO 0957+561A/B, was discovered with the 2.1-m telescope at Kitt Peak by Walsh et al. (1979).

Many others have since been found, often serendipitously, from radio observations with the VLA, from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey, from the WISE observatory, and others. Subsequent observations with the Hubble Space Telescope provide some of the highest-quality images.

As of December 2019, the Gravitationally Lensed Quasar Database listed 220 confirmed lensed quasars. These discoveries provide the basis for follow-up observations, time variability studies, and detailed modelling.

Today, new systematic searches of the entire sky have been made possible with Gaia. And over the past two years, the multi-national Gaia Gravitational Lenses working group (GraL) has discovered about 10% of all currently confirmed strongly lensed quasars, including 12 of the 56 known quadruply-imaged quasars.

ALTHOUGH GAIA DOES NOT produce images of the sky in the conventional sense, its effective angular resolution in the along-scan direction is nevertheless comparable to that of the Hubble Space Telescope.

Thus, amongst the previously known quadruple-image quasars, 29 have at least one image in the Gaia DR2 data release, and 12 of these have all four images detected (Ducourant et al., 2018). These authors went on to show, for example, that the well-known quadruple HE 0435–1223 has model parameters significantly better constrained when using Gaia astrometry compared to HST astrometry, in particular for the relative positions of the background quasar, and the lens centroid.

Gaia is accordingly providing the first homogeneous, magnitude-limited census of strongly lensed quasars over the entire sky, down to lensed image separations of about 0.18 arcsec. And indeed, even prior to the first data release, it was estimated that of the more than 500 000 quasars expected to be detected by Gaia down to $G < 20$ mag, some 3000 would be resolved, multiply-imaged quasars, of which only some 1600 would have image separations large enough to be resolved by ground-based atmospheric-limited observations (Finet & Surdej, 2016).

THE GRAL TEAM employs various methods to identify resolved multi-image lenses in the Gaia data. One uses supervised machine-learning to identify candidates based on their Gaia astrometry and photometry.

Another discovery technique is to use quasar light curves (e.g. from the Catalina Real-Time Transient Survey and the Zwicky Transient Facility), supplemented by Gaia astrometry and photometry. Underpinning this technique is that, for an unresolved lensed system, the observed time series is the addition of multiple identical light curves with time delays which, compared to an unlensed quasar, results in a less stochastic light curve.

In the sixth paper of their GrAL series, Stern et al. (2021) identified possible quadruple-lensed systems in the Gaia DR2 data release, then used various spectroscopic observations (using the Keck telescope in Hawaii, the Palomar Hale, and the ESO NTT and the Gemini-South telescopes in Chile) to confirm or refute candidates based on their spectral similarities. In this way, they identified a total of 12 confirmed quadruply-imaged quasars, one example being shown here.

The 12 confirmed quadruply-imaged Gaia quasars

Stern et al. (2021)

Several other groups are also using the Gaia data, along with machine learning and other supplementary observations, to find these rare systems, some of which are already noted in my earlier essay on Gaia quasars (#12). Amongst these are the discovery of a five-image lensed quasar at $z = 3.34$ using data from Gaia and Pan-STARRS1 (Ostrowski et al., 2018).

THESE NEW DISCOVERIES set the stage for various multi-wavelength follow-up activities, with some of the grand cosmological objectives mentioned in the introduction. Besides photometric monitoring, which will enable their use as cosmological probes, follow-up campaigns include high-resolution radio observations, X-ray observations, and near-infrared adaptive optics integral field unit spectroscopy to improve the source modelling.

At X-ray wavelengths, several of these quadruples have already been observed with ESA's XMM-Newton, starting in July 2020 (Connor et al., 2022). As an example, the image at 0.3–8.0 keV of GrAL J1651–0417 shows exactly the same features detected by Gaia, indicated here by the white circles.

Connor et al. (2022)

These and future X-ray observations will assist in the detailed modelling of the lensing source, since a typical quiescent lensing galaxy will not contribute a significant X-ray flux. But they may also provide estimates of black hole spins at redshifts $z > 3$, the size of the X-ray emitting region, and even X-ray spectral analysis at high redshift due to the magnified X-ray flux.

NEW PHYSICAL and cosmological insights, as well as many more new lensed quasars based on future improved Gaia data releases, will surely be arriving with us in the very near future.

Stern et al. (2021)